

Zero-Cost Specialized Measuring Tool for Wirebond IMC

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Abstract—This paper presents a specialized measurement grid tool for wirebond intermetallic coverage (IMC), with zero-cost implementation.

Keywords— IMC; intermetallic coverage; wirebond; grid tool.

I. PROJECT OBJECTIVE

- Provide specialized measurement tool for quantifying or measuring wirebond intermetallic coverage (IMC) and other IMC-related anomalies, for New Product Introduction (NPI) and Assembly Process Control
- Zero-cost implementation by utilizing existing software licenses and available resources
 - Instead of purchasing brand-new measurement equipment or software measurement tool, one great challenge is to come up with an innovative and cost-effective solution by maximizing existing/available resources

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION – WIREBOND IMC WITH VISUAL MEASUREMENT

- Previous methodology utilized manual grids to measure or estimate the magnitude of the IMC

IMC for Gold wire:
 Accept if $\geq 75\%$
 Reject if $< 75\%$

Fig. 1. Example of Gold (Au) wire ball impression.

III. SOLUTION IMPLEMENTATION

BEFORE	AFTER
<p>Manual Grid</p>	
<p>Loss: Low accuracy. Measurement is subjective, and through visual estimation.</p>	<p>Gain: Measurement is still subjective but with better accuracy. The tool calculates real-time while pin-pointing the non-IMC part (light-colored). You can also choose to pin-point the dark-colored part.</p>
<p>Result: IMC (dark-colored) covered a total of 30 grid boxes out of 36. Hence, measured % IMC is estimated at 83.33%.</p>	<p>Result: % IMC is at 86.71%. The measured value is of better accuracy and credibility than the visual manual grid estimation.</p>